

Numerical Analysis and Mechanical Design of a Solar-Powered Floating System for Seawater Desalination

Hussein Sabah Hashim ✉

Department of Drilling Techniques and Oil and Gas Production,
Samawah Technical Institute, Al-Furat Al-Awsat Technical University, Iraq

Article History:

Received: 06.02.2026 Revised: 11.03.2026 Accepted: 13.03.2026 Published: 14.03.2026

ABSTRACT:

The research includes a new method for desalinating seawater using a floating solar still with forced cooling. The research also involves a numerical study of the system in several stages using the Cosmos Flow Works package, which is part of the SolidWorks suite. The results include the distribution of temperatures of the liquid, metal, and fins, as well as the flow lines and velocities of the cooling water movement in the lower half.

Keywords: Floating System, Seawater, Solar-Powered System, forced cooling.

Suggested Citation: H.S. Hashim, "Numerical Analysis and Mechanical Design of a Solar-Powered Floating System for Seawater Desalination," *Eur. J. Appl. Sc. Eng. Technol.*, vol. 4(2), pp. 148-162, Mar-Apr 2026. DOI: 10.59324/ejaset.2026.4(2).09

INTRODUCTION

Water is one of the fundamental conditions for life on Earth; there is no life without water. The presence of water led to the establishment of the first human civilizations, and wherever water is found, life and civilizations thrive. Due to the enormous increase in population, rising living standards, and industrial and agricultural development, water sources have become polluted and limited. Because of the scarcity of freshwater sources on Earth, the problem of severe water shortage has emerged.

Many studies and research have been conducted on the future of the freshwater situation and the search for new freshwater sources other than traditional ones, such as desalinating saline water. Therefore, it is necessary for us to conduct the necessary studies and research on how to utilize the seawater around us. Based on the above, the idea of this research emerged, which is the desalination of seawater by utilizing solar energy [1].

The intensity of solar radiation is one of the most important factors affecting the performance of solar stills, as the productivity of the still decreases with the decrease in the value of the solar radiation falling on the surface of the cover and vice versa. Various desalination methods with high production capacity, reaching hundreds of thousands of cubic meters of freshwater, have been invented. Desalination methods have multiplied and diversified, including distillation, reverse osmosis, electro dialysis, ion exchange, and solar energy desalinate [2].

Research Objectives

The importance of the research lies in the fact that most traditional methods for desalinating saline water consume a large amount of energy, require a significant number of equipment that occupy

This work is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License. The license permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, on the condition that users give exact credit to the original author(s) and the source, provide a link to the Creative Commons license, and indicate if they made any changes.

large areas, and have high equipment and maintenance costs. The following system was studied due to its distinctive features:

1. The system is completely independent and not linked to any other system, so it does not require any external energy sources.
2. The energy provided is small and obtained through photovoltaic solar cells.
3. The spherical shape advantage: It helps in receiving solar rays from all directions throughout the day.
4. No additional energy is required for cooling the desalinated water due to the presence of fins, as the stability of the seawater temperature is utilized.
5. The primary material (saline water) is available and free.
6. The salt formed on the absorbing plate can be utilized.

The research objectives can be summarized in several points, which are:

- Develop an algorithm that represents the physical phenomenon occurring within the still.
- Analytically study the effect of various parameters on the amount of water produced and the thermal efficiency of the still.
- Perform computer simulations and review the factors affecting the fluid within the still.
- Study the thermal distribution field of the cooling water along the length of the condenser.
- Study the thermal distribution field on the body of the condenser.

REFERENCE STUDIES

Many studies and research have addressed the topic of water desalination, particularly desalination using solar energy. In 2008, Z. Haddad et al. [3] linked a spherical solar still with a flat collector and studied the effect of several parameters on the experiment's performance, leading to an increase in production and system performance improvement, with a yield increase of between 9-12%. In 2009, R. Jayaprakash et al. [4] analyzed the performance of a spherical solar still with two different thicknesses of low-density polyethylene (0.176 mm and 0.107 mm) for the upper cover. They observed that the evaporation rate was higher for the thinner cover, which was also less costly, and the maximum yield reached 22%. In 2009, Rajesh et al. [5] conducted an experimental study comparing the performance of a simple dual-slope solar still with a flat plate collector (FPC). They performed experiments on spring, river, and seawater and studied their effect on productivity. They concluded that productivity varies according to solar density, and distillation productivity increases by 42% for spring water, 45% for river water, and 40% for seawater in the presence of a collector.

In 2012, T. Arunkumar et al. [6] conducted experiments where the upper cover was cooled by water. They observed that the driving force for solar desalination technology differs between the temperature of the water in the distillation basin and the temperature of the upper cover (TW-TC), and the yield increased from 34% to 42% for a constant flow rate of saline water at 10 ml/min.

In 2012, T. Arunkumar et al. [7] conducted an experimental study comparing the performance of two solar stills: a pyramid-shaped still and a hemispherical still, both with the same area of 1 m². They observed that both types provided high water temperatures, and there was a significant difference in evaporation and condensation rates due to the design of the upper cover. The yield reached 32.02% for the pyramid still and 26.59% for the hemispherical still, indicating that the hemispherical still performed better than the pyramid still.

In 2012, Hitesh N Panchal et al. [8] conducted an experiment with a hemispherical solar still under the climatic conditions of MEHSANA, GUJARAT. This article discusses a new design for the hemispherical solar still with and without cover cooling. They concluded that the still's yield reached more than 18%, and the daily production of distilled water was between 1.4-1.6 liters. In 2014, Ajayraj S Solanki et al. [9] studied the effect of black ink in a hemispherical still with different water depths

and a fixed volume of ink inside the water. They found that the still's productivity increased with decreasing water depth, and adding 1% black ink increased the still's productivity from 17% to 20%. Adding 2% black ink increased the still's productivity to 25%, and the maximum productivity was achieved between 1-2 PM.

In 2014, Palak Pate et al. [10] introduced a set of improvements to the passive still and studied the effect of these improvements on productivity. Using sprinklers increased productivity by 14%, cooling the glass cover had a significant effect on increasing the temperature difference between ($T_w - T_g$), and experiments showed that 10 mm black rubber increased the productivity of the deep still by 20%. Black gravel with a size of 20-30 mm increased the productivity of the shallow solar still by 19%, and using charcoal as an absorbent material increased productivity by 10%. Using black dye increased productivity by 29% compared to red dye on the deep basin more than the shallow basin. In 2015, Ahmed J. Mohammed et al [11] built a hemispherical solar still and evaluated its performance under the weather conditions in Basra, Iraq. It consisted of a basin with an area of 20.025 m², and the practical productivity and yield of the solar still were calculated. They observed that the majority of the distillation output was obtained between noon and sunset, where the yield of the hemispherical solar still reached 19-23%, and the highest yield value reached 23% on September 16, 2013. Distillation productivity increased as the temperature of the saline water increased.

In 2016, A.E. Kabee et al. [12] conducted an experimental comparative study of water production from a traditional single-slope solar still and a modified still using a new technique to heat the surface of the saline water through a finned cover with holes. These fins were used to increase the heat transfer area between the cover and the surface of the saline water. The stills were tested at a water depth of 0.05 m and a saline water volume of 50 liters. They found that at a constant water depth, the amount of clean water per square meter of the modified system was higher by about 20% daily compared to the traditional system. At a constant volume of saline water, the amount of drinking water produced by the modified system was higher by about 30% compared to the traditional system. In (2016), Sonu J. et al. [13] introduced several techniques to the spherical solar still with the aim of increasing productivity, such as heating the incoming water, the used an appropriate thickness for the glass cover from 2 mm to 6 mm. They found that using wick material to increase the surface area of the water in the basin by 20%, and cooling the condenser section, which increases productivity by using the incoming water as a coolant.

Summary of Reference Studies

- It was observed that most previous studies were experimental, through which daily productivity and yield were obtained.
- It was observed from previous studies that the spherical shape has a more positive effect on productivity compared to other shapes (such as pyramidal, etc.).

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The system consists of a spherical solar still for desalinating seawater by utilizing solar energy.

System Components

Figure 1 illustrates a schematic diagram of the system for the spherical solar still with all its components.

The system consists of a sphere composed of two halves. The upper half is made of glass and is used to receive solar radiation. Condensers are installed around the periphery of this section of the sphere to condense the vapor resulting from the evaporation of seawater. Additionally, buoyancy aids are attached to help stabilize the sphere in the sea, preventing it from being affected by the vibrations caused by sea waves. The lower half of the sphere is made of metal with fins and is filled with pure water to act as a cooling medium in the vapor condensation process. Fins are placed in the lower half of the sphere to increase the surface area, thereby utilizing the fins in the cooling process of the pure water to maintain its temperature stability. Several materials can be chosen for the upper half, including (window glass, low-density polyethylene) [14,15].

Figure 1. A Preliminary Schematic Plan for the Solar Distiller System with Its Components

Condenser: It is a heat exchanger used to remove the heat drawn from the water vapor to condense it with the help of a cooling medium.

Types of Condensers

1. Air-cooled condensers: Use air as a condensation medium.
2. Water-cooled condensers: Use water as a condensation medium.
3. Evaporative condensers: Use both water and air as a condensation medium.

In this research, the condenser will be chosen to consist of a corrugated tube fixed on a plate placed on the inner surface of the upper hemispherical section.

Insulating Plate: Due to the difference in temperatures between the cooled space (the lower half of the sphere) and the upper half, heat will transfer from the upper half of the sphere to the lower half. To separate the two halves, an insulating plate is placed, which functions as thermal and water insulation with an air gap.

Absorbing Surface: It is a black plate, which absorbs solar radiation, and stores its heat, thereby raising the temperature of the saline water above it. It is worth noting that the insulating plate and the absorbing surface are integrated.

Collection Tray: It is used to collect condensed water droplets to obtain pure water.

Buoyancy Aids: They are used to stabilize the system in the sea, preventing it from being affected by the vibrations caused by sea waves, thereby ensuring its continuous operation. It is worth noting that the effect of vibration on the condensation and evaporation process has not been studied due to its complexity and is not within the scope of this research.

Pump: It is used to pump the cooling water to the condensers to contribute to the condensation process, and then the water returns to the basin (the lower section). It is operated by electrical energy generated by photovoltaic cells placed on the

Level Controller: It is used to determine the water level above the plate, forming a thin layer above the plate, thus absorbing heat from the sun more quickly.

System Operation Principle

The model consists of a sphere with its upper half made of glass to receive solar radiation and the lower half made of metal with fins filled with fresh water. Seawater is pumped in at a certain flow rate

determined by a level controller. As solar radiation gradually falls, thermal accumulation occurs, leading to an increase in the temperature inside the still. This causes the water above the plate to heat up, resulting in the evaporation of part of the water into vapor that rises upward. Upon hitting the internal glass surface of the still, a heat exchange occurs between the vapor and the surface. Due to the temperature difference between vapor and the external surface of the still (which is in contact with the surrounding medium), condensation occurs, and condensed water droplets slide down under the influence of gravity to collect in the side pockets and exit as fresh water.

Here, condensation of the vapor occurs, and the droplets slide under the influence of gravity into the side channels (collection tray) where they accumulate, thus obtaining pure water. As long as there are temperature and pressure differences, the evaporation and condensation process continues [16].

Condensation is facilitated by a cooling medium, which is the freshwater present in the lower half of the sphere. The condensed water droplets (the produced water) collect in the collection tray, while the hot water returning from the condenser to the lower half of the sphere has its heat dissipated through the fins attached to the periphery of the lower half of the sphere.

It is important to note that the energy inputs to the still equals the outputs. To obtain a quantity of fresh water equal to M . The radiation passing through the cover is divided into two parts:

- The water at the base of the still absorbs the first part, and it is assumed that the remaining part is directly transmitted to the surrounding medium through the cover without any reflection or absorption by the cover.
- The second part is reflected from the water surface.

Numerical Simulation

The numerical study of this system was conducted using the Cosmos FlowWorks package, which is part of the SolidWorks 2009 suite. This package is a powerful tool for engineers to evaluate aerodynamic processes and heat transfer processes, and it relies on numerical solution techniques like other packages.

Cosmos Flow Works stands out from other (CFD) packages with the following features:

- Inputting initial data and viewing results are done in a single window within the program.
- A regular engineer can use this package without the need for specialized engineers as required by other packages.
- The relatively short time required to prepare initial data and view results.

However, there is one drawback to this package: it is considered an add-on to the SolidWorks program and only works within its environment.

Governing Equations

Continuity equations: They express mass flux per unit area, given for the gas phase as follows:

$$\bar{V} \cdot (r_G \rho_G V_G) + S_{LG} = 0 \quad (1)$$

Where: \bar{V} : Relative velocity (local velocity referred to a maximum velocity).

r_G : Volumetric fraction of vapor, ρ_G : Density of vapor, V_G : Velocity of vapor, and S_{LG} : Mass flux of the fluid referred to a unit surface area.

Liquid phase:

$$\bar{V} \cdot (r_L \rho_L V_L) - S_{LG} = 0 \quad (2)$$

R_L : Volumetric fraction of Liquid, ρ_L : Density of Liquid, V_L : Velocity of Liquid.

Equations of Motion: It represents the effect of vapor pressure on its motion mechanism, as the mass and heat transfer between the vapor and the surface alters the vapor pressure, thus leading to condensation, for the gas phase:

$$\bar{V} \rho_G (r_G V_G V_G) = -r_G \bar{V} P_G + \bar{V} (r_G \mu_{Laminar G} (\bar{V} V_G + \bar{V} V_G)^2) \rho_G + r_G \rho_G g l_G - M_{GL} \quad (3)$$

Liquid phase:

$$\bar{V} \rho_L (r_L V_L V_L) = -r_L \bar{V} P_L + \bar{V} (r_L \mu_{Laminar L} (\bar{V} V_L + \bar{V} V_L)^2) \rho_L + r_L \rho_L g l_L + M_{GL} \quad (4)$$

Energy equations: for the gas phase:

$$\bar{V} \cdot (r_G \rho_G V_G h_G) = -\bar{V} \cdot q + (Q_{LG} + S_{LG} h_{LG}) \quad (5)$$

Liquid phase:

$$\bar{V} \cdot (r_L \rho_L V_L h_L) = -\bar{V} \cdot q - (Q_{LG} + S_{LG} h_{LG}) \quad (6)$$

Volume conservation equations:

$$r_L + r_g = 1 \quad (7)$$

Mass transfer equations: for the gas phase:

$$\bar{V} \cdot (r_G (\rho_G V_G Y_A - \rho_G D_{AG} (V Y_A))) - S_{LG} = 0 \quad (8)$$

Liquid phase:

$$\bar{V} \cdot (r_L (\rho_L V_L X_A - \rho_L D_{AL} (V X_A))) - S_{LG} = 0 \quad (9)$$

Simulation of the System as a Phase Change Case

Problem Description

Figure (2) shows a cross-section of the solar distiller, indicating all the boundary conditions applied during the simulation:

Material Type Specification

- The inlet and outlet plugs for the condenser cooling water are made of insulating materials.
- The material of the condenser tube and its plate is red copper.
- The thermal resistance between the plate and the condenser tube is negligible.
- The largest distance between two nodes in the mesh is 35[mm], and the smallest is 1 [mm].
- The diameter of the absorber plate is 60 [cm]

Problem Boundary Conditions

1. The vapor stream flow rate above the plate is 0.000013 [m²/s].
2. The inlet water temperature for the condenser is 20 [°C].
3. The diameter of the inlet opening is 8 [mm].
4. The glass temperature is constant at 29 [°C].
5. The water flow rate entering the condenser is 0.16 [kg/s].

Several simplifications were made to the system to enable the simulation of the upper part and obtain acceptable results. It was assumed that vapor at a temperature of 60[°C] rises from the absorber plate. In the C.F.W package, there are automatic examples for meshing. The finer the mesh, the greater the accuracy, but the solution becomes more difficult. Cosmos, however, has surpassed the meshing evaluation stage; it does not begin the solution if the mesh does not meet the solution criteria. Furthermore, it automatically corrects errors during the solution process.

Figure 2. The Boundary Conditions Applied to the System at a Vapor Temperature of 60°C

Computational Simulation Results for the System

Table 1 shows the data for the simulation mesh of the distiller. It includes details on mesh discretization, the number of volumetric cells used, and the number of iterations per travel.

Table 1. Shows the Simulation Data for the Distiller as a Phase Change Case

Parameter	Value
Fluid cells	107567
Solid cells	32611
Partial cells	143049
Iterations	526

Computational Simulation of the Condenser Only

Problem Description

Figure 3 shows a cross-section of the condenser. It should be noted that in this case, only one condenser was considered to simplify the simulation process.

Figure 3. General View of the Condenser Located in the Upper Part of the Solar Distiller, which Contains Two Opposing Condensers

Material Types of the Upper Part Components and Problem Boundary Conditions:

- The inlet and outlet plugs for the condenser cooling water are made of insulating materials.
- The material of the condenser tube and its plate is red copper.
- The thermal resistance between the plate and the condenser tube is negligible.
- The largest distance between two nodes in the mesh is 8 [mm], and the smallest is 1 [mm].

Problem Boundary Conditions:

1. The inlet flow rate of the condenser cooling water is (-10.001) [m²/s].
2. The inlet water temperature (-2293) [K].

The diameter of the inlet opening is 8 [mm]

Computational Simulation Data for the Upper Part:

Table (2) shows the data for the computational simulation mesh of the upper part (condenser) of the distiller, with details on mesh discretization and the number of volumetric cells used, as well as the number of iterations per travel.

Table 2. Simulation Data for the Upper Part

Parameter	Value
Fluid cells	469
Solid cells	18436
Partial cells	39283
Iterations	225
Last iteration finished	13:59:17
CPU time per last iteration	00:01:12
Travels	
Iterations per 1 travel	78
Cpu time	0:59:38
Calculation time left	0:0:0
Status	

Computational Simulation of the Lower Part of the Spherical Solar Distiller

Problem Description:

Figure 4 shows a cross-section of the lower part of the solar distiller. Before simulation, it is necessary to define the material types of the components of the lower part and the boundary conditions for the problem:

- The upper cover and the inlet/outlet plugs for the cooling water are made of insulating materials.
- The material of the lower part's metal with its fins is aluminum.
- The thermal resistance between the fins and the body of the lower distiller is negligible.
- The largest distance between two nodes in the mesh is 3 cm, and the smallest is 1 [mm].

Figure 4. General View of the Lower Part of the Solar Distiller

Boundary for the problem:

1. The inlet flow rate of cooling water for the condenser is 0.001 [m³/s].
2. The inlet temperature of the water (returned after condensation) is 319 [K].
3. The inlet opening diameter is 8 [mm].
4. The inlet temperature of seawater is 293 [K].

5. The flow velocity of seawater at the inlet is 0.2 [cm/s]. See Figure (3-13).

Figure 5. Cross-Section Showing the Inlet and Outlet Openings for Seawater and Condenser Cooling Water

Computer Simulation Data

The computer simulation data for the lower section of the distiller was performed with the assistance of the Cosmos Works package within the SolidWorks environment. Table 3 illustrates the details of the meshing and the number of successive approximation stages.

Table 3. Simulation Data for the Lower Section of the Distiller

Parameter	Value
Fluid cells	21793
Solid cells	970
Partial cells	30880
Iterations	302
Last iteration finished	13:12:11
CPU time per last iteration	00:00:57
Travels	
Iterations per 1 travel	76
Cpu time	1:19:53
Calculation time left	0:0:0
Status	Solver is finished

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Simulation Results of the System as a Phase Change Case

Figure 6 illustrates the flow lines of the liquid and vapor streams within the system. Random streams of vapor and liquid are observed under the hemispherical dome, as well as liquid flow streams within the condensers. Regarding the water flow within the condenser, an increase in the cooling water temperature is noted from the moment of entry to the moment of exit, where it discharges into the lower part of the distiller.

Figure 6. Flow Lines of the Liquid and Vapor Streams within the System

Graphical Plot Resulting from Simulation along the Central Line

A graphical plot was obtained from the previous simulation under the mentioned boundary conditions. Figure (7) illustrates the fluid temperature distribution within the system along the central line originating from the center of the plate and extending towards the top of the spherical dome. It is observed that in the region close to the plate, the vapor temperature is high. With gradual movement away from the plate towards the dome, a significant decrease in vapor temperature is noted for two reasons:

1. Because of heat exchange with the cover.
2. As a result of heat exchange with the condenser surface, which is considered a cold surface and effectively contributes to increasing the condensation process and reducing the vapor temperature until it stabilizes at a constant temperature.

The constant temperature at 30°C indicates that condensation (phase transition from vapor to liquid) occurs at this temperature.

Figure 7. Temperature Distribution of the Fluid within the System

Simulation Results for the Upper Section of the Distiller (Condenser)

Figure 8 illustrates the thermal distribution field on the condenser body. It is observed that the region of the plate far from the condenser tube has a higher heat transfer coefficient. Concurrently, the region of the tubes and the surrounding plate body has a lower heat transfer coefficient and thus a

lower temperature. This latter region is the one most likely to condense the water vapor rising from the bottom of the distiller.

The temperature distribution field of the condenser cooling water along its length is shown in Figure (9). It is observed that the water temperature gradually increases as it approaches the outlet opening.

Regarding the thermal current distribution field transferred to the condenser tube due to different thermal loads, it is observed that the ends of the tube are exposed to a larger thermal current, as shown in Figure (10). While figure (11) illustrates the flow lines of the cooling water stream, with its flow velocity variations superimposed. It is observed that the cooling water velocity in the condenser tube decreases slightly due to the constant cross-section of the tube and the smoothness of its surface.

Figure 8. Thermal Distribution Field on the Condenser Body

Figure 9. Temperature Distribution Field of the Condenser Cooling Water Along Its Length

Figure 10. Thermal Current Distribution Field Transferred to the Condenser Tube

Figure 11. Flow Lines of the Cooling Water Stream, with its Flow Velocity Variations Superimposed

Simulation Results for the Lower Section of the Distiller

Figure 12 illustrates the thermal distribution field according to the frontal plane. It is observed that the lower region has a higher heat transfer coefficient. This behavior is also evident in Figures 13 and 14.

The temperature distribution of the condenser cooling water within the lower half of the distiller is shown in Figure 15. The temperatures are loaded onto the streamlines. It is observed that the cooling water enters at a higher temperature, and as it flows within the lower half, its temperature changes significantly due to cooling.

Figure 16 shows the flow lines distribution of the condenser cooling water within the lower half of the distiller. The different velocity values along the flow lines are also evident. It is clear that the inlet

point has a high velocity, which then begins to decrease as it opens into the larger lower hemisphere of the distiller.

The thermal field distribution on the inner surface of the lower hemisphere is shown in Figure 17. It is observed that the surface opposite the condenser cooling water inlet (after its return from the upper part) exhibits the highest temperatures. This position (the surface opposite the condenser cooling water inlet, which has the highest temperatures) can change with variations in the injection location of the water returning from the upper part.

Figure 12. Thermal Distribution Field According to the Frontal Plane

Figure 13. Thermal Distribution Field According to the Lateral Plane

Figure 14. Thermal Distribution Field for the Upper Plane

Figure 15. Temperature Distribution of the Condenser Cooling Water within the Lower Half of the Distiller

Figure 16. Velocity Distribution of Condenser Cooling Water within the Lower Half of the Distiller

Figure 17. Thermal Field Distribution on the Inner Surface of the Lower Hemisphere

CONCLUSIONS

The bottom region, specifically at the base, is the hottest compared to other regions. The same result was obtained when taking cross-sections.

- The water returning from condensation is at a high temperature, and consequently, the corresponding opening has a high temperature.
- The inner surface in the lower part of the sphere, opposite the aforementioned opening, also has a high temperature. This region will experience a significant heat flux through the fins.
- The region most likely to experience greater water vapor condensation is the plate region compared to the tube region, as it has a higher heat transfer coefficient.
- In the condenser tubes, it is observed that the region near the condensation water outlet has a higher heat transfer coefficient. This result is logical when compared to the findings from studying the lower section, where the surface opposite the (condensed water return) opening also showed a higher heat transfer coefficient.
- The cooling water flow velocity in the condenser tube is generally almost constant. However, due to the tube geometry (presence of local losses), slight variations in velocity are observed.
- In the fluid temperature distribution diagram, the constant temperature at 30 degrees indicates that condensation (phase transition from vapor to liquid) occurs at this temperature. Obtaining a good temperature difference for the vapor in the studied system highlights the role of the condensers.

REFERENCES

- [1] S. A. Kalogirou, *Solar Energy Engineering: Processes and Systems*, 2nd ed. Amsterdam, Netherlands: Academic Press, 2014. <https://doi.org/10.1016/C2011-0-07038-2>.
- [2] V. Pawar and S. Sobhansarbandi, "Computational fluid dynamics modeling of a heat pipe evacuated tube solar collector integrated with phase change material," in *Proc. ASME International Mechanical Engineering Congress and Exposition*, 2019, Paper IMECE2019-10252, pp. 1–13.
- [3] Z. Haddad and N. Boukerzaza, "Coupling of a spherical solar still with a collector," *International Journal of Soft Computing*, vol. 3, no. 4, pp. 317–321, 2008.
- [4] R. Jayaprakash, K. Perumal, T. Arunkumar, S. Kumar, and B. Selvakumar, "Design and performance analysis of low cost solar still using transparent LDPE cover," *Journal of Environmental Research and Development*, vol. 4, no. 2, pp. 465–474, 2009.
- [5] M. Rajesh and N. Bharath, "Solar still coupled with solar collector and storage tank," *InterJRI Science and Technology*, vol. 1, no. 2, pp. 62–72, 2009.
- [6] T. Arunkumar, R. Jayaprakash, and D. Denkenberger, "An experimental study on a hemispherical solar still," *Desalination*, vol. 286, pp. 342–348, 2012. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.desal.2011.11.047>
- [7] T. Arunkumar, R. Jayaprakash, and A. Ahsan, "A comparative experimental testing in enhancement of the efficiency of pyramid solar still and hemispherical solar still," *International Journal of Renewable Energy Research*, vol. 2, no. 2, pp. 210–213, 2012.
- [8] H. Panchal, V. Prajapati, R. Goswami, and N. Pancholi, "Performance analyses of hemispherical solar still in climate condition of Mehsana, Gujarat," *International Journal of Advanced Engineering Research and Studies*, vol. 1, no. 3, pp. 1–4, 2012.
- [9] A. S. Solanki, U. R. Soni, and P. Patel, "Comparative study on hemispherical solar still with black ink added," *International Journal of Engineering Research and General Science*, vol. 2, no. 3, pp. 315–324, 2014.
- [10] P. Patel, A. Solanki, U. Soni, and A. Patel, "A review to increase the performance of solar still: Make it multilayer absorber," *International Journal on Recent and Innovation Trends in Computing and Communication*, vol. 2, no. 2, pp. 173–177, 2014.
- [11] A. Mohammed, N. Abdullah, and J. Al-Asadi, "Evaluating thermal efficiency of hemispherical solar still (HSS) (circular basin) in Basra City-Iraq," *Journal of Basrah Researches (Sciences)*, vol. 42, no. 1A, pp. 121–130, 2015.

- [12] A. E. Kabeel, M. M. Bassuoni, and M. A. Rozza, "Experimental study for new design solar still," in *Proc. 19th International Water Technology Conference (IWTC19)*, 2016, pp. 103–111.
- [13] S. J. Sharma and K. V. Modi, "Techniques to improve productivity of spherical solar still," *International Journal of Advance Research and Innovative Ideas in Education (IJARIIE)*, vol. 2, no. 3, pp. 997–1000, 2016.
- [14] H. S. Mickley and T. K. Sherwood, *Applied Mathematics in Chemical Engineering*. New York, NY, USA: McGraw-Hill, 2008.
- [15] H. Panchal and P. K. Shah, "Modeling and verification of hemispherical solar still using ANSYS CFD," *International Journal of Energy and Environment*, vol. 4, no. 3, pp. 427–440, 2013.
- [16] A. Shafieian, M. Khiadani, and A. Nosrati, "A review of latest developments, progress, and applications of heat pipe solar collectors," *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, vol. 95, pp. 273–304, 2018. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2018.07.014>.

